

**CREATIVE RESEARCH IN DOMESTIC CINEMA:
PRINCIPLES AND ACHIEVEMENTS**

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Abstract: National cinematography, like other aspects of our nation's life, is in the process of continuous research and development. The results of these studies are shown in the form of films of various content. This article focuses on scripts and directors' works and their audience in cinematography.

Key words: Film, script, director, screen, work, cameraman, camera work, actor, art.

**МИЛЛИЙ КИНОДАГИ ИЖОДИЙ ИЗЛАНИШЛАР:
ТАМОЙИЛ ВА ЮТУҚЛАР**

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Аннотация: Миллий кино санъати миллатимизнинг бошқа жабҳалари сингари мудом изланиш, ривожланиш жараёнини бошдан кечирмоқда. Бу изланишлар самараси турли мазмунли киноасарлар тимсолида бўй кўрсатади. Кино санъатида сценарий ва режиссура яратилган асарлар ва уларнинг томошабинбоплиги ҳақидаги фикрлар ушбу мақолада эътиборга олинади.

Калит сўзлар: Кино, сценарий, режиссёр, экран, асар, оператор, кинематография, актёр, санъат.

**ТВОРЧЕСКИЕ ИССЛЕДОВАНИЯ В ОТЕЧЕСТВЕННОМ
КИНЕМАТОГРАФЕ: ПРИНЦИПЫ И ДОСТИЖЕНИЯ**

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Аннотация: Национальное киноискусство, как и другие аспекты жизни нашей нации, находится в процессе непрерывных исследований и развития. Результаты этих исследований показаны в виде фильмов различного содержания. В данной статье основное внимание уделяется сценарным и режиссерским произведениям и их зрительской аудитории в кинематографе.

Ключевые слова: Фильм, сценарий, режиссёр, экран, произведение, оператор, операторская работа, актёр, искусство.

INTRODUCTION

If we want to glorify the memory of our ancestors, on this basis we want to glorify the Uzbek name, the name of Uzbekistan throughout the world, we must do this primarily through the art of cinema. It is thanks to cinema that we can conquer the world's screens and thus attract the attention of people around the world.

Mirziyoyev Sh.M.

METHODS

Uzbek cinema has its own rich heritage, distinguished by a variety of styles and colors. From the beginning of the 20th century to the present day, domestic cinematography has experienced different stages and periods. Each period, each stage with its achievements and shortcomings, ups and downs has its own significance.

In 2017, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Miromonovich Mirziyoyev signed a resolution "On measures for the further development of domestic cinematography" . The decision is based on the objectives defined in the Action

Strategy for five priority areas of development of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2017-2021, and, first of all, on enhancing the role of cinematography, which has a great influence in educating young people about the ideas of national independence, respect for national and universal values, and a sense of love for the Motherland. Particular attention was paid to measures to improve the activities of the National Agency "Uzbekkino".

As a result, the demand for the production of our national films increased. This marked the beginning of a new era in the film industry - the emergence of private film studios. This created creative competition, and the world of cinema began to rise significantly.

At the same time, the demand for cinematography, which is the basis of cinematography, increased. One of the main requirements was the reflection of real and life problems, events that worry many people. When a person is depressed, he sometimes looks for a way out through cinema. Thus, the creation of an image that reveals the nature of a person's mental state, actions and behavior began to be considered as the next task of filmmakers.

ESULTS AND DISCUSSION

"Thinking about the artistic integrity of Uzbek cinema, first of all, it is appropriate to think about the cooperation of the scriptwriter and director and the trend based on this criterion. After all, "if the pain of the author on paper and the pain of the director, embodied in life on the stage, are in harmony and harmony, if the maslak comes from the same place, then the success and longevity of the work will be ¹. " Important and priority tasks remain the promotion of domestic cinematography, the creation of high-quality and quantitative films, work on the necessary measures to ensure the development of this industry.

Of course, it is appropriate to say that one can pay attention to the screen interpretations of such works as "Alisher Navoi", "Tahir va Zuhra", "Otkan Kunlar",

¹Mukhamedov M. Basics of directing. - T.: UzDSMI, 2008. - B.10.

"Scorpion from the Altar", "Shum Bola". in our national literature. The point is not in what period they were created or to what nation they belong, but in what features distinguish them as literature or cinema. Why is a film in many cases more popular than a work, why is a film product well remembered by most viewers? At this point, the difference between cinema and literature becomes clear. The reason is very simple: cinema has such a unique "weapon" that literature does not. This is visibility, that is, image.

Because "the viewer is primarily influenced by the visual side of the film - the visual solution. If the visual solution of the film does not go beyond the narrative style, then this is the level of a mediocre film. Therefore, the modern viewer does not like it very much," ²says film critic Khanjara Abulkasimova. The strength of the film that you actually watch, the image, the acting, especially the strength of the script, is manifested in the skill of the director. Today, art historians and film critics are called upon to play a major role in the development of this area. Famous actors, directors and playwrights who occupy their place in the world of art are considered special professions.

In Uzbek cinema S. Abdulla, I. Sultan, T. Tola, A. Ramazonov, R. Faiziy, M. Shaikhzoda, A. Mikhalkov-Konchalovsky, S. Mukhamedov, O' Umarbekov, R. Mukhammadjonov, E. Akopov., Sh. In films created by the creative collaboration of such authors as Boshbekov and M. Toychiev, there are aspects that will not lose their significance in ideas and themes not only yesterday, but also today, and if necessary, tomorrow. "Tahir and Zukhra" also had great success in the field of cinematography. In this area, turning to Uzbek folk tales, legends, historical figures and events enriched Uzbek cinema.

The feature film "Alisher Navoi" went down in history as a highly artistic film dedicated to the life and work of Alisher Navoi, a historical hero of not only the Uzbek but also the Turkic peoples, the sultan of the gazelle of flour. In 1967, director Yuldosh Azamov shot a film based on the work of the founder of the Uzbek

²Abulkasimova H. Basics of Cinematography. - T.: National Encyclopedia of Uzbekistan, 2009. - B.32.

novelization Abdulla Kadiri "Otkan Kunlar" and became a masterpiece of the Uzbek artist. It must be said that the film "Past Days" also appeared as a unique phenomenon in Uzbek cinematography in terms of its appeal to elements of nationalism. In the events of the work, such qualities as pure love, Uzbek idioms, sentiments, loyalty are expressed in bright colors of the screen and to this day are able to impress the viewer on the screen. Uzbek is proud that this film has great educational value.

When we express our opinion about Uzbek cinema, it is appropriate to mention the name of Shukhrat Abbasov, who made a great contribution to the Uzbek film school with his directorial work. In the director's film "Mahalla Duv-Duv Gaap", folk culture is revealed on the basis of deeper and deeper events and expressions. In addition, the film also contains a subtle reference to the problems of the era and the social lifestyle of people.

It is known that the events of the film are born, develop and end during the process of huge construction projects in the city. At the time when old low-rise houses and buildings are massively demolished and replaced by high-rise modern buildings, a conflict arises in the film between the older representatives of the "old time" and the young people of the new era. According to the older people in the film, the youth does not care about national values and traditions. According to the youth, it is necessary to change many customs and traditions of the people. In their opinion, this is what the times require.

Shukhrat Abbasov and the creators of the film "Mahalla Duv-Duv Gaap" very skillfully develop such a symbolic and eternal social conflict, and ultimately make it a beautiful and unique ending. That is, in any era and century there was a conflict between the old and new generations. This is an old theme. This contradiction is also found in the film "Mahalla Duv-Duv Gaap" and ends with the "reconciliation" of representatives of both generations. Such films opened a bright page as a product of successful creativity.

In the first years of independence, cinematography acquired a special significance in the history of Uzbek cinema due to the diversity of different eras, different processes

and various themes. In this process, the genre, plot, trends in the national and folk key were formed and developed. In this regard, along with a number of development processes in the field of cinema, it is appropriate to recognize some problems and shortcomings. For example, when showing some films of the National Agency "Uzbekkino", the number of viewers in cinemas is small, cinematography is developing at a slow pace, genres and themes in most films are very similar to each other. dramaturgy is small, the ideas expressed in films are not important, camera work is not important, such complex problems as the impossibility of finding an adequate visual and artistic solution were observed.

After the 2000s, with the arrival of such filmmakers as Hilal Nasimov, Yolkin Toychiev, Ayub Shakhobiddinov in the film industry, the process of solving serious and serious topics in the film industry was directly visible in their work, and it was noted that they had their own fans. Thanks to the discoveries and successful creative approaches of the director, the ideas of the films found a clear and effective expression.

Hilal Nasimov. In films such as "Deceived Woman", "Tubanlik", "Classmates", "Gumrokhlar" and "Azhal Dousi", the influence of the character of the hero captivates the viewer throughout the film. As for the film, its meaningful depth, rich in observations that include sore points of society, attracts us all. Cinematography has a great responsibility in this process so that our citizens do not fall into the clutches of the growing religious extremist movements in the world. In the film "Deceived Woman", which is constantly broadcast on television, the rise of terrorism and human trafficking is shown through the heroine Mahira, who is the main factor that allows us to appreciate a peaceful and peaceful life. The fact that the director skillfully attaches importance to every detail and every frame always calls the viewer to be on guard. Each character has pain, inner character and has something to say. Because the character of the heroes is reflected in very impressive, unexpected processes. Hilal Nasimov worked very carefully on the script during the writing process, paying special attention to the dialogues of the characters to enhance its impact. This encourages the viewer to be attentive. When watching the events of the film, it immediately comes to

mind that these events could have happened to any of us. The characters of the actors are played based on the inner world of each character. In the film, after the words of Amir Abu Bakr: "Let everyone forget the word hijrat, henceforth pour into the ears the words of jihad and martyrdom", of course, it is gratifying that Mahira realized her mistake. The viewer in every way pities the dead woman, wants to believe in her innocence, is angry at her terrible, disgusting life in slavery. At the end of the film, viewers will closely watch what happens to Mahira, who has experienced so much pain and left prison, receiving a punishment befitting her crime against the Motherland. Repenting of her mistakes and actions, Mahira is left alone, shedding thousands of tears of regret for her country and her family. The director uses Mahira's character as an example of many deceived women, victims of fate, separated from their families. In this film, the director calls not only women but the entire nation to be conscious.

The director's work of Ayub Shakhobiddinov deserves a special description of the uniqueness of his work. His film "Otov" contains deep ideological content. The main character of the film Ubaidulla "repents" of the regime of the former Soviet Union. Tuzum was the fate that first separated him from his parents, and then from his wife. What he found in life will remain with his only son. That is why he goes to the mountains, away from people and society, and grows grass there. And he begins to live in the grass. He tries to protect his only son from the system he created. The fact that the meaning of his life became his only son, and later his wife and little girl, shows his bitter fate.

The educational value of the Uzbek language is great, care for the elderly is visible in many films. Despite the fact that the film "The Old Man and the Grandson" is created in the comedy genre, it attracts attention with a wealth of acute psychological situations and dramatic situations. The actions of the father to get rich, not receiving news from his family, the fate of the children and the pain of the father, who is the head of the family. At first glance, it seems that the old man should solve the problems of his grandchildren. However, the old man also learns a lot from his grandson based on conversations with his grandson. Even a small little child plays an important role in

solving the problems happening in the heart of the old man. In such comedies, the main weapon of laughter is based on words and intellectual ingenuity. The scriptwriter is required to express the thought of a sharp mind on the spot, in short, capacious sentences.

In the film, the author expressed the character of the old man in a unique conflict. He is shown as angry, gloomy and always in a dissatisfied mood. When he speaks, he speaks not from the heart, character and mood of the interlocutor, but from the essence of the matter, from the point of view of truth. As a rule, in society, "good people" are considered to be people who speak from the heart, are polite and do not speak harshly to others. However, the peculiarity of this comedy is that the director, through the image of this "bad man", tries to show that not all concepts that have developed in society are true, that a person of real conscience cannot be so meek and meek.

People's Artist of Uzbekistan Polat Saidkasimov, whose roles we have been following since childhood, expressed his character very sparingly and thoughtfully. The quality of the Uzbek people, its national characteristics in the film will please the viewer with their originality, integrity and honesty. Such films are, of course, pleasant and watchable.

CONCLUSION

It is known that art, especially cinema, plays an important role in shaping the spirituality of the people and the consciousness of the youth. In this regard, filmmakers bear a huge responsibility. In turn, creating works of art for our people, who have high spirituality, values, rich historical traditions and great ancestors, is a double responsibility. So to speak, today the creators of domestic cinema, feeling this responsibility on their shoulders, are creating in the field of cinema by leaps and bounds. And domestic cinema is constantly striving for the heights and is developing in the spirit of aspiration, search and competition.

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